

Why Does Ministerial Ethic Matter?

Mutabazi Placide*^{1,2}, Sangwa Sixbert^{1,3}, Niyitegeka Jean Pierre⁴

¹Open Christian University, South Africa

²Mount Kenya University, Rwanda

³Africa Leadership University, Rwanda,

⁴University of Rwanda, Rwanda

*Email: muplacidus@gmail.com

Abstract: God calls us to walk humbly with Him. The Christian ministry is one ordained by God for a special purpose in His Kingdom (Exodus 40:12-15). The ministry as ordained by God, it is the noblest work on earth, nurture the flock, lead them to win lost souls and leads in the warfare against the devil and his host of demons (Ephesians 6:12). Christians should resist the temptation to construct a pharisaical list of do's and don'ts but rather look for biblical ethical principles to guide our decision-making (Goldingay, 2018). These can be summed up in the commandments to “love God with all our heart, soul and mind” and “to love our neighbor as ourselves” (Mt 22:37-40). This paper discusses the principles of ministerial ethics based on Ten Commandments as written by God on stone and then recorded by Moses in the Bible's book of Exodus (Gorman, 2009). The paper suggest that we should recognize that true Christian morality involves going beyond the mere letter of the law (Mt 5:21-22, 27-28) to the very spirit of love on which it is based (1Cor 13:4-8).

Key word: Authority, Commandments, Christian, Ethics, God, Ministry, Principles, Sovereignty, stewardship.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ethics is the science of morality (Horrell, 2018). Its task is to examine the moral aspect of human nature and behavior, to clarify issues in moral decision-making and moral dilemmas, and to facilitate formation of moral character (Gushee& Stassen, 2016). In Micah 6:8, we find a helpful definition of morality. It can be argued on the information found in that passage that morality asks four questions (Verbrugge, 2000): 1) What is *good*? Not what is normal, legal or acceptable in a given culture, but rather, what is good. 2) What is *just*? Human beings are born with rights, to

which they have God-given right. Immoral conduct consists in denying these rights to our fellow human beings (Horrell, 2018), 3) What is *kind*? Our relationships and our inter-human conduct must be kind and compassionate and the means we use to reach the above moral qualities must be carefully scrutinized by knowing that God calls us to walk humbly with Him (Gushee & Stassen, 2016).

2. DESCRIPTION OF MINISTERIAL ETHICS

This part discusses the Christian ministry and ethical principles from the Bible with reference to Ten Commandments as written by God on stone and then recorded by Moses in the Bible's book of Exodus (Gorman, 2009).

2.1 The Christian Ministry

The Christian ministry is one ordained by God for a special purpose in His Kingdom (Exodus 40:12-15; I Peter 2:5, 9; John 15:16). The ministry consists of a family of people called by God for special service to Christ and His flock. The ministry as ordained by God: 1) Is the noblest work on earth. No profession can be compared to it. 2) Is aimed at nurturing the flock and leading them to win other lost souls to Christ (Jeremiah 23:4; John 21:15-17). 3) Is spiritual and holy (John 4:24; I Peter 1:16), and 4) Is leading in the warfare against the devil and his host of demons (Ephesians 6:12)

2.2 Ethical Principles from the Bible perspectives

We should resist the temptation to construct a pharisaical list of do's and don'ts but rather look for biblical ethical principles to guide our decision-making [9]. These can be summed up in the commandments to 'love God with all our heart, soul and mind' and 'to love our neighbor as ourselves' (Mt 22:37-40). While respecting the Ten Commandments, we should recognize that true Christian morality involves going beyond the mere letter of the law (Mt 5:21-22, 27-28) to the very spirit of love on which it is based (1Cor 13:4-8). The following principles are based on the Ten Commandments.

2.2.1 The Sovereignty of God

You shall have no other Gods before me (Ex 20:3)

God is the Creator (Gn 1:1), the Sustainer (Heb 1:3) and the Lord of all life. He is also absolute arbiter of right and wrong and has spoken clearly in history through his word and through his Son Jesus Christ (Heb 1:1-2), in whom all his fullness dwells (Col 1:19). We must always put him first.

2.2.2. Stewardship

You shall not make for yourself an idol (Ex 20:4-6)

God has made us stewards of his creation and guardians of the planet (Gn 1:26,28). This validates scientific enquiry and application but is not a license for exploitation, nor for seeing medicine rather than God as humankind's savior. We must always exercise our delegated authority for good, especially for the good of individual human beings. Furthermore, we should do it according to God's revealed standards of right and wrong. The end does not justify the means.

2.2.3. Honoring God's character

You shall not misuse the name of the Lord your God (Ex 20:7)

We must recognize and acknowledge God as the real source of all good gifts (Jas 1:17; 1 Cor 4:7) upholding his compassion, grace, patience, love, faithfulness, forgiveness and justice (Ex 34:6,7); and not bringing dishonor to his name in our words or actions; nor should we seek glory for ourselves.

2.2.4. Work and Rest

Remember the Sabbath Day... six days shall you labor (Ex 20:8-11)

We have an obligation to work (2 Thes 3:10-13), to serve others in order to provide for our own needs and those of our family (1 Tim 5:8) and to imitate God who is himself a worker. But we must also honour and recommend the Creator's rule of one day's rest in seven, recognising that it was made for our pleasure and benefit (Is 58:13-14; Mk 2:27) and as a sign of the rest to come (Heb 4:9-11).

2.2.5. Authority and the Family

Honor your father and your mother (Ex 20:12)

God has established human authorities as his agents to serve and protect us and we should submit to them and not rebel against their authority (Rom 13:1-7). Most important among these is the family which is God's provision for the protection, nurture and discipline of children (Dt 6:6,7; Eph 6:1-4) and the stability of society as a whole.

1.2.6. The Sanctity of Life

You shall not murder (Ex 20:13)

All human life is made in God's image (Gn 9:6, 7) and is worthy of the utmost respect from its beginning to end. This includes the unborn (Ps 139:13-16; Is 49:1; Jb 10:8-9), the handicapped (Lv 19:14), the vulnerable (Ex 22:21-24) and the advanced in age (Lv 19:32). The heart of Christianity is that we must love as Christ himself loved (Jn 13:34), that the strong should lay down their lives for the weak (Phil 2:5-8, Rom 5:6-8).

2.2.7. Sexuality and Marriage

You shall not commit adultery (Ex 20:14)

Marriage is a life-long, publicly recognised, heterosexual, monogamous relationship (Gn 2:24; Mt 19:4-6; Eph 5:31-33) and is representative of Christ's own relationship with the church. Sex is God's good gift for intimacy (Mt 19:4), pleasure (Pr 5:18,19) and procreation (Gn 1:28) but must only take place within the marriage relationship (Barton, 2016).

2.2.8. Respect for property

You shall not steal (Ex 20:15)

God has blessed human beings materially in order that they may provide for their own needs and those of others (2 Cor 9:8). We should show respect for the property of others and seek to use what he has given us in accordance with his revealed will.

2.2.9. Veracity

You shall not give false testimony (Ex 20:16)

We should 'speak the truth in love (Eph 4:15) at all times, using our words to build others up rather than tearing them down. Lying through commission or omission runs counter to the nature of God himself (Nu 23:19) and leads to injustice. We should be people of our word (Jas 5:12).

2.2.10. Contentment

You shall not covet... (Ex 20:17)

We should be grateful and content with what God gives us (Phil 4:11-12), not being driven by jealousy or desire for the possessions, relationships, gifts or honor of others. Rather we should desire to do his will, to have his gifts to serve others (1 Cor 12:31) and most of all to desire God himself (Ps 37:4), knowing that he will provide us with what we need.

3. CONCLUSION

The Christian ministry is one ordained by God for a special purpose in His Kingdom (Exodus 40:12-15; I Peter 2:5, 9; John 15:16). It is the noblest work on earth, nurture the flock, lead them to win lost souls and leads in the warfare against the devil and his host of demons (Ephesians 6:12). Christians should look for biblical ethical principles to guide their decision-making. These can be summed up in the commandments to “love God with all our heart, soul and mind” and “to love our neighbor as ourselves” (Mt 22:37-40).

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